

“Project identity: brand, marketing basics and website”

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05/2024	<i>final version resubmitted to Participant Portal</i>	V2.0

SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. It aims to build upon pre-existing IAC mechanisms such as EIT KICs and to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalised nature, our project pilots the mechanism's two main components: a methodology developed by applying human-centred design principles and an online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and at supporting them throughout their co-creation journey.

The INDUSAC methodology provides the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform stands as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting at least 300 transnational co-creation teams throughout the project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components will be successively improved until the project ends, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. It is expected for INDUSAC to also create a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including at least 1000 companies, 3000 students and 300 researchers by project end. The INDUSAC counts with a strong interdisciplinary, cross-sectorial and geographically balanced partnership that counts with the needed expertise and network to achieve our project's goals.

ABSTRACT

This document is the second deliverable of Work Package 4 – Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication. The aim of this deliverable, D4.2, is to provide the concept and guidelines for the project partners with the unique project brand, identity, logo, and project marketing basics (website, social media, flyer, roll-up, etc.), which were developed by a professional design agency. It is considered an ‘ongoing’ process, so, if necessary, the presented marketing materials will be updated and improved during the implementation of the project.

LIST OF ACRONYMS

BIC	Bydgoszcz Industrial Cluster Tool Valley, member of the INDUSAC consortium
EU	European Union
INDUSAC	Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation mechanism for INDUSty Academia Collaborations
M	Month
T	Task
WP	Work Package

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I. INTRODUCTION

The INDUSAC project's brand identity and visual design are crucial for its recognition and differentiation. The official logo, chosen collaboratively by the team, reflects the project's mission and includes a circle symbolizing collaboration. The Brand Book provides guidelines for the consistent application of visual elements across all communication channels. Partners have access to templates and resources, ensuring uniformity in messaging.

Social media platforms such as Twitter and a YouTube channel are used to engage stakeholders and disseminate project-related content. The INDUSAC website serves as a central hub for project information, including updates, funding opportunities, news, and promotional materials.

The branding and communication strategy is essential for fostering collaboration and disseminating project outcomes, maximizing its impact and stakeholder engagement. All these tasks are carried out within the framework of D4.2.

II. BRAND

1. Visual identity

The visual identity tools have been designed to distinguish the project through a clear and simple image that allows it to be easily recognised. During the first two months of the project, the consortium selected a final version of the official logo of the partnership by voting.

C:6 M:18 Y:94 K:0
R: 245 G: 204 B: 0
#f5cc00

C:90 M:78 Y:1 K:0
R: 57 G: 70 B: 150
#394696

C:12 M:9 Y:10 K:0
R: 229 G: 228 B: 228
#e5e4e4

C:53 M:42 Y:38 K:22
R: 120 G: 120 B: 125
#78787d

C:91 M:79 Y:62 K:97
R: 0 G: 0 B: 0
#000000

Figure 1 : Official INDUSAC logo with the colour palette.

The official font used in the INDUSAC logo is Futura. For text, the official font of INDUSAC is Nunito Sans. Alternatively, the Calibri font can be used in communication within the consortium, e.g. in documents, emails, etc.

The main version of the logo is presented with the colour palette shown in Figure 1. The alternative (negative) versions of the logo are shown in Figure 2. Negative versions may be used when there is no option for colour displays or printing.

Figure 2 : Alternative versions of the INDUSAC logo.

The INDUSAC logo has two key elements: the symbol and letters. The symbol forms a circle that resembles co-creation and collaboration. The circle is divided into three parts representing the capacity of the participants: Academia (students and researchers), Companies, and Digital Tools. The composition of the INDUSAC partnership directly responds to the need to have cross-sectorial experts from the academic and industrial world who are well-connected to existing industry-academia collaboration mechanisms, together with experts in digital open innovation. The letters include the project's acronym INDUSAC in bold typography. The typography is simple and direct. The RGB values are presented in Brand Book.

All dissemination activities, including promotional materials, have been adapted and are in line with the colour palette and font style of the logo.

The full version of the guide on how to use the visual identity of INDUSAC is described in the Brand Book. The Brand Book and logo can also be downloaded from the project's official website under the 'Communication Toolkit' tab.

2. Templates

During the first six months of the INDUSAC project, BIC, as the T4.1 leader, prepared a poster template to be used by the consortium members whenever necessary or appropriate in communication and dissemination activities. It has been designed in line with the project's visual identity.

All templates are available for partners in the dedicated WP4 Communication and Dissemination folder on the project's cloud.

III. MARKETING BASICS

1. Social Media

A Twitter account has been launched for the INDUSAC project: twitter.com/INDUSAC_HE.

Figure 3 : INDUSAC Twitter account (https://twitter.com/INDUSAC_HE).

Partners will post about INDUSAC activities through their corporate and personal social media accounts, and participate actively in LinkedIn groups for various project areas.

Social media channels will allow the project to share important messages for quick dissemination and to establish a virtual dialogue with the same channels of stakeholders, including relevant projects and initiatives. All partners are encouraged to be active on the INDUSAC social media, share posts from the project's official account, invite more people to follow, etc.

2. Flyer

The INDUSAC flyer was designed in M3 and will be updated in M32 to add information on the results achieved during the project (APPENDIX 3).

The flyer contains overall information and a brief description of the INDUSAC project. It includes a map with the logotypes of the partners and the EU logo with a disclaimer. The flyer will be provided electronically to be forwarded via e-mail and as downloadable content from the website; furthermore, there will also be printed versions to be used for

conferences and physical events. The flyer can be downloaded from the website: 'Communication Toolkit' tab and on the project's cloud in the WP4 folder.

3. Roll-up

The roll-up was designed in M3 and will be updated in M32 (APPENDIX 4).

The roll-up will be used at all physical events to increase the visibility of the INDUSAC project (Figure 4 : Official INDUSAC Roll-up). This type of promotional material will help to inform potentially interested stakeholders and the general public about the INDUSAC project. The roll-up includes a slogan, the official project's website, logotypes of the partnership, and the EU logo with the disclaimer. The project roll-up can be found on the project's cloud in the WP4 folder.

INDUSAC

Quick Challenge-Driven, Human-Centered
Co-Creation Mechanism for
INDUstry-**Academia** Collaborations

 Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement No 101070297.

Figure 4 : Official INDUSAC Roll-up.

4. Press release

Information about the project, open call, its activities, and results will be distributed in the form of press releases. These will be sent to regional, national, European, and other international media. Partners will be able to adapt them to their corporate language and circulate them throughout their own communication channels. The press releases can be downloaded from the website: 'Media' tab and on the project's cloud in the WP4 folder.

5. Video

Figure 5 : INDUSAC channel on YouTube.

The INDUSAC YouTube channel has been created (Figure 5). This is a space where short videos and animations, as well as recordings of project-related webinars and events, and any other similar videos about the project, can be uploaded. These will be shared on the INDUSAC website, social media, and other dissemination channels. All official videos of the project will be added to the WP4 folder on the project's cloud.

6. General presentation

A general PowerPoint presentation has been prepared with reference to a general project presentation. This document entails visual information about the most important and reliable facts and figures about the project.

The presentation is available on the project's cloud (under the WP4 folder), and it will be used by all partners during the events promoting the INDUSAC project.

IV. WEBSITE

A dedicated project website was prepared in M6. The official domain is: www.INDUSAC.eu

The objective of the website is to serve as a vehicle for the dissemination of the project activities and results. The main focus of the website is external communication. The project website is also developed to encourage information sharing between the members of the consortium and the general public.

Under the overall guidance of BIC, all consortium partners are responsible for actively contributing to the information on the website. It is planned to publish project-related news and events attended or organised by partners, and other topics related to the project.

Figure 6 : INDUSAC website – slider

Figure 7 : INDUSAC website – open call

INDUSAC

INDUSAC'S MAIN OBJECTIVE IS TO DEVELOP AND VALIDATE A STATE-OF-THE-ART, INDUSTRY ACADEMIA COLLABORATION MECHANISM FOR QUICK, CHALLENGE-DRIVEN, HUMAN-CENTRED CO-CREATION.

The aim of the Quick Challenge-Driven, Human-Centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUSTRY-Academia Collaborations (INDUSAC) project is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia Collaboration mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation.

The INDUSAC project designs a state-of-the-art mechanism for the industry-academia collaboration that is based on human-centred design principles that enable quick project co-creation. At least 300 international co-creation projects are selected for implementation to ensure the validation of the mechanism. These micro-projects led by teams consisting of students, researchers, and company staff are involved across various activities to target numerous industrial sectors. They are expected to create a bridge between business and academia.

Figure 8 : INDUSAC website – about project section

Figure 9 : INDUSAC website – methodology section

PARTNERSHIP

THE CONSORTIUM FORMED BY TOP ACADEMIC INSTITUTIONS, PRIVATE INNOVATION ACCELERATORS, AND INDUSTRIAL CLUSTER ASSOCIATIONS ALREADY HAS ABOUT 1000 STAKEHOLDERS INCLUDING STUDENTS, RESEARCHERS, AND COMPANIES.

Figure 10 : INDUSAC website – partners logo section

Figure 11 : INDUSAC website – news section

About Partners

Figure 12 : INDUSAC website – consortium partners

Figure 13 : INDUSAC website – communication toolkit section

Figure 6 - 13 represents the homepage. The website is divided into five sections:

- 1) 'About':

- a. 'INDUSAC' – information about the project,
 - b. 'About Partners' – a map with logotypes and descriptions of all partners,
 - c. 'Project committees' – information about the committees participating in the selection and execution process.
- 2) 'Funding opportunities':
 - a. 'Open Call' – general information and a link to the application website.
 - 3) 'News & Events':
 - a. 'Upcoming events' – general information about the events with links to the details/registration form, etc.,
 - b. 'Past events' – archive of the events.
 - 4) 'Media' with the most important promotional materials, e.g. press releases,
 - 5) 'Communication toolkit' with the Brand Book and all versions of the INDUSAC logo and flyer available to download.

On the website, you can also find links to INDUSAC's Twitter and YouTube profiles. On the footer of the home page, one can find the EU flag with the disclaimer and a contact form which offers users the possibility to address questions or comments through an official online form.

The architecture of the website is simple, user-friendly, and developed in a WordPress template. The graphical elements are in line with the visual identity of the project. The website includes Google Analytics to monitor traffic on the website. The content of the website is updated regularly.

V. ANNEXES

ANNEX 1 : Brand Book

ANNEX 2 : Poster Template

ANNEX 3 : Flyer

ANNEX 4 : Roll-up

ANNEX 5 : Press Release

ANNEX 6 : General Presentation

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TECHNOLOGY CENTER

UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA
DE CATALUNYA
BARCELONATECH

**BAX
& COMPANY**
VALUE FROM SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

BYDGOSZCZ
INDUSTRIAL CLUSTER
TOOL VALLEY

 **Cyprus
University of
Technology**

 KIT
Karlsruhe Institute of Technology

 eit Manufacturing
CLC EAST

Co-funded by the
European Union

 innoget

INDUSAC

B R A N D S T Y L E G U I D E

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INTRODUCTION

INDUSAC **designed** a state-of-the-art **mechanism for industry-academia collaboration** that is based on **human-centred** design principles and that enables **quick co-creation** projects. Its **two main components** (its underlying **methodology** and its **online platform**) are being developed and validated through the piloting of at least **300 transnational co-creation projects** involving teams of **students, researchers, and company staff** and targeting numerous industrial sectors across the cross-cutting areas of **circularity** and **general sustainability, digitalisation** and **industry 4.0**. The consortium formed by top academic institutions, private innovation accelerators, industrial cluster associations, and knowledge and innovation communities of the EIT already have +960 stakeholders including students, researchers and companies within their reach.

**LOGO
MAIN VERSION**

INDUSAC

SAFETY AREA

The safety zone of the INDUSAC logo was determined by the use of a module that is 100% of the size of the small circle in the sign.

There must be no foreign text or graphic objects in this space.

MINIMUM SIZE

TYPOGRAPHY

The **Futura PT** brand is a uniform style procedure, consisting of seven weights with corresponding obliques as well as 8 condensed types. Each of these fonts are coordinated in letterforms, metrics, and weights to operate superior alongside one another.

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg

ALTERNATIVE TYPOGRAPHY

Nunito Sans is a simple and welcoming typeface. It makes for great headline and body text. It also is a great alternative font for Futura because it has many of the same features. For example, Nunito Sans features a more open “c” just like Futura has.

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg

COLOUR PALETTE

INDUSAC

C:6 M:18 Y:94 K:0
R: 245 G: 204 B: 0
#f5cc00

C:90 M:78 Y:1 K:0
R: 57 G: 70 B: 150
#394696

C:12 M:9 Y:10 K:0
R: 229 G: 228 B: 228
#e5e4e4

C:53 M:42 Y:38 K:22
R: 120 G: 120 B: 125
#78787d

C:91 M:79 Y:62 K:97
R: 0 G: 0 B: 0
#000000

**LOGO
ALTERNATIVE
VERSIONS**

APPLICATION ON A BACKGROUND

The logo in the basic version looks best on a white background and it should be used this way most often. If it is necessary to use it on a dark background, the inscription should be presented in white. If the sign on a dark background is not legible, the achromatic option can be used.

INCORRECT USE

Don't change the colours.

Don't change the typography.

Don't replace the order of the elements.

Don't place on an aggressive background.

www.indusac.eu

ANNEX 2: Poster Template

LOREM IPSUM DOLOR

LOREM IPSUM DOLOR SIT AMET

20th March 2023

LOREM IPSUM

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet consectetur adipiscing elit sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat volutpat. Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exerci tation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat.

LOREM IPSUM DOLOR SIT AMET

LOREM IPSUM DOLOR SIT AMET

LOREM IPSUM

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LOREM IPSUM DOLOR SIT AMET

INDUSAC

**Quick Challenge-Driven,
Human-Centred Co-Creation Mechanism
for INDUStry-Academia Collaborations**

- PROJECT INFORMATION -

www.indusac.eu

PROJECT GOAL

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia Collaboration mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation.

The INDUSAC project designs a state-of-the-art mechanism for industry-academia collaboration that is based on human-centred design principles that enable quick project co-creation. At least 300 international co-creation projects are selected for implementation to ensure the validation of the mechanism. These micro-projects led by teams consisting of students, researchers, and company staff cover various activities to target numerous industrial sectors. They are expected to create a bridge between business and academia.

The INDUSAC project focuses on four areas: circularity, general sustainability, digitalisation and industry 4.0.

The INDUSAC project creates a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders.

1000
companies

3000
students

300
researchers

PLATFORM

The aim of the platform is to build on pre-existing Industry-Academia Collaboration mechanisms to facilitate a user-friendly co-creation process. It provides the foundation for developing solutions that clearly process the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU.

METHODOLOGY

The aim of the methodology is to facilitate the creation of company, student and researcher teams by matching industry needs with students and researchers interests and skills. The methodology is built on a baseline of pre-existing co-creation approaches and offers guidance packages, as well as processes and tools for its smooth functioning. It provides detailed user journey maps.

THE INDUSAC CONCEPT

Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

The project coordinator

Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
Germany

Cyprus University of Technology
Cyprus

Bax & Company
Spain

EIT Manufacturing East
Austria

UPC Technology Center (CIT UPC)
Spain

Innoget
Spain

Bydgoszcz Industrial Cluster
Tool Valley
Poland

Chamber of Commerce and Industry
of Pécs-Baranya
Hungary

Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Co-funded by the
European Union

TECHNOLOGY CENTER
CENTRO POLITÉCNICO
DE INVESTIGACIÓN
INDUSTRIAL

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement No 101070297.

www.indusac.eu
twitter.com/INDUSAC_HE

INDUSAC

Quick Challenge-Driven, Human-Centred
Co-Creation Mechanism for
INDUStry-Academia Collaborations

start

BRIDGE
science & business

CHALLENGES
(companies)

COOPERATION

TEAMS
(students
& researches)

**OPEN
CALL**

PLATFORM

finish

www.indusac.eu

twitter.com/INDUSAC_HE

Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Programme under grant agreement No 101070297.

The Quick Challenge-Driven, Human-Centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations (INDUSAC) is a HORIZON EUROPE project.

The aim of the project is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art Industry-Academia Collaboration mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation.

The INDUSAC project designs a state-of-the-art mechanism for industry-academia collaboration that is based on human-centred design principles that enable quick project co-creation. At least 300 international co-creation projects are selected for implementation to ensure the validation of the mechanism. These micro-projects led by teams consisting of students, researchers, and company staff cover various activities to target numerous industrial sectors. They are expected to create a bridge between business and academia.

The INDUSAC project focuses on four areas:

- Circularity
- General Sustainability
- Digitalisation
- Industry 4.0

1000
companies

3000
students

300
researchers

The INDUSAC project creates a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including at least 1000 companies, 3000 students, and 300 researchers by project end.

The project focuses on the mechanism's two main components:

➤ **The INDUSAC platform** is to build on pre-existing Industry-Academia Collaboration mechanisms to facilitate a user-friendly co-creation process. It provides the foundation for developing solutions that clearly process the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU.

➤ **The INDUSAC methodology** aims to facilitate the creation of company, student, and researcher teams by matching industry needs with students' and researchers' interests and skills. The methodology is built on a baseline of pre-existing co-creation approaches and offers guidance packages, as well as processes and tools for its smooth functioning. It provides detailed user journey maps.

Open Calls

INDUSAC launches a continuous open call for universities. The aim is to engage with at least 15 organisations at the start of the open call and reach at least 30 by the end of it. The open call for universities and research centres will be open for 18 months, starting in September 2023. Once registered in the open call, the universities and research centres will promote participation in the competitions among their students, who will be able to express interest, join a team and submit their solutions to companies' challenges anytime during the open call. Each challenge will have a specific deadline during the open call, which will be announced two months in advance to allow a suitable reaction from the companies and students. INDUSAC will select 300 co-creation teams formed by at least three students from three different EU countries, who will receive the INDUSAC programme support grant.

The project started on 1st September 2022 and will run for three years.

Partnership

The project coordinator is Jožef Stefan Institute (Slovenia) and other partners are Bydgoszcz Industrial Cluster Tool Valley (Poland), Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Pécs-Baranya (Hungary), Cyprus University of Technology (Cyprus), Bax & Company (Spain), UPC Technology Center (Spain), EIT Manufacturing East (Austria), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (Germany), and Innoget (Spain).

INDUSAC

Quick Challenge-Driven, Human-Centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations

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Partnership

Jožef Stefan Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia
Project coordinator

EIT Manufacturing East
Austria

UPC Technology Center (CIT UPC)
Spain

Innoget
Spain

Bax & Company
Spain

Bydgoszcz Industrial Cluster
Tool Valley
Poland

Chamber of Commerce and Industry
of Pécs-Baranya
Hungary

Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
Germany

Cyprus University of Technology
Cyprus

About INDUSAC

The project aims to develop and validate a state-of-the-art Industry-Academia Collaboration mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation.

- The INDUSAC project designs a state-of-the-art mechanism for industry-academia collaboration.
- At least 300 international co-creation micro-projects selected for implementation ensure the validation of the mechanism.
- Micro-projects led by teams consisting of **students**, **researchers**, and **company staff** cover various activities to target numerous industrial sectors.

1000
companies

3000
students

300
researchers

The INDUSAC project creates a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including at least **1000** companies, **3000** students, and **300** researchers by project end.

The project is piloted by two mechanisms

M
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THE INDUSAC CONCEPT

Open Calls

INDUSAC will launch a continuous Open Call for universities. The aim is to engage with at least **15** organisations at the start of the open call and reach at least **30** by the end of it.

INDUSAC will select 300 co-creation teams formed by at least 3 students from 3 different EU countries, with a focus on gender balance and on broadening the group of countries that will receive the INDUSAC programme support grant.

The project implementation started on
1st September 2022
and will run for three years.

Contact

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